

Zinc kinetics correlate with length-for-age z scores in Bangladeshi
infants

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Abbreviations: A_{\max} , maximum absorption of zinc; IA_{50} , quantity of zinc required for half-maximal absorption; CTU, Clinical Trial Unit; EED, Environmental enteric dysfunction; ICP-MS, inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry; LAZ, length-for-age z score; WAZ, weight-for-age z score; WLZ, weight-for-length z score; Zn, zinc

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: Stunting (length-for-age z score, LAZ < -2) has multiple causes and is prevalent in areas with low dietary zinc (Zn) intake. Zinc kinetics from non-stunted infants were used in a published model for predicting linear growth; here we directly measure zinc kinetics in stunted infants.

Methods: Zinc kinetics were determined in 9-mo old Bangladeshi infants (n=10), who were non-wasted (weight-for-length z score (WLZ) \geq -2), ranging in LAZ from -2.9 to -0.43. Stable isotopes were administered 2 h after a meal as oral (^{70}Zn) and intravenous (^{67}Zn) tracers. After isotope administration, blood was sampled within 5 h and all urine and feces were collected for 24 h. Urine was sampled twice-daily out to 9 days. Data were analysed by compartmental modeling. Daily zinc intake was estimated by the model as the sum of zinc used for growth plus that lost via urine and feces. Zinc absorbed (the amount required to maintain steady state) was the sum of zinc used for growth plus urine and endogenous fecal excretions.

Results: The LAZ score correlated with serum zinc concentration (R=0.77, P=0.001), urinary zinc excretion (R=0.66, P=0.010) and fractional zinc absorption from calculated daily intake (R=0.58, P=0.030). In stunted infants (n=8) the amount of zinc absorbed did not increase with calculated zinc intake unlike published values for non-stunted infants.

Conclusions: Zinc kinetics in Bangladeshi infants correlate with LAZ and show that malabsorption of supplemental sources of zinc may occur in stunted infants.

Key words: homeostasis, kinetic modeling, simulation

What is known

- Zinc is required for linear growth.
- Growth of zinc-deficient stunted infants improves with zinc supplementation.
- Compartmental models of zinc metabolism can assist in designing zinc dosing regimens.

What is new

- Zinc kinetics correlate with LAZ scores.
- Stunted Bangladeshi infants absorb less zinc from calculated daily zinc intake and absorption saturates at lower zinc intakes than non-stunted infants.
- This absorption limitation has implications for zinc supplementation of stunted infants, namely the need to ensure that the supplements are being absorbed.

INTRODUCTION

Linear growth in early childhood is a marker of future development (1). In many low-resource countries the prevalence of stunting (length-for-age z score, LAZ < -2) remains high (e.g., 28% in Bangladesh (2)). Stunting can result from multiple causes including inadequate intake of essential micronutrients (1), chronic infections (3), and conditions such as environmental enteric dysfunction (EED), an alteration of the gut by frequent infections (4).

The prevalence of stunting is higher in populations with inadequate zinc intakes (5), and zinc supplementation increases linear growth (6). The effects of supplementation may be greater in children older than 2 y (7) but the optimal window for preventing growth faltering is up to 2 y of age (8).

Zinc deficiency in in Bangladeshi children aged 6-59 mo is 41% (9). To improve zinc status, the optimal zinc dosing regimens (amount, frequency and duration) need to be determined (5). To address this issue, we published a mathematical model of zinc metabolism in infants (10). An assumption of the infant mathematical model was that zinc kinetics did not vary with LAZ (10). However, the growth rates of zinc-supplemented stunted infants (11) were only fit by the model if zinc absorption was reduced by one-half, i.e., 0.15 vs. 0.30 (10).

Thus, the aim of the current study was to measure zinc kinetics in 8-11 month-old non-wasted (weight-for-length z score, (WLZ) \geq -2) infants from a population with a high prevalence of zinc deficiency, over a range of LAZ, from normal to stunted (< -2 LAZ) and to use the results to update the model for predicting linear growth (10).

METHODS

The zinc stable isotope studies were performed at the Clinical Trial Unit (CTU) located at the International Centre for Diarrhoeal Disease Research (icddr,b) in Dhaka, Bangladesh, between Feb – Sep 2019. Infants arrived the day before tracer administration, and remained in the CTU for 24 h after tracer administration. Spot urine samples were collected out to 9 d.

Participants: This was a sub-study of a larger trial in infants and study infants (n=10) were recruited as for the parent trial (12). Inclusion criteria included infants aged 8-11 months of age with LAZ > -3, living in the peri-urban community of Bauniabadh, Dhaka. LAZ below -3 SD is considered severe stunting and may represent a higher likelihood of underlying growth-limiting systemic conditions beyond nutritional and environmental causes. Exclusion criteria included the presence of acute malnutrition (WLZ < -2 and/or the presence of bipedal edema and/or mid-upper arm circumference < 115 mm); congenital anomalies or conditions that interfere with feeding; chromosomal anomalies and other organic problems; acute diarrhea.

Ethics: The study was approved by the Research Review and the Ethical Review Committees of icddr,b and the University of Colorado Multiple Institutional Review Board. Mothers of the participant infants gave written informed consent prior to participating.

Zinc Isotope Tracers: Intravenous ^{67}Zn and oral ^{70}Zn stable zinc isotopes were prepared at the University of Colorado Anschutz Medical Campus (CU) in the Pediatric Nutrition Laboratory as described previously (13, 14). Tracers were tested for fungus, sterility,

and pyrogens prior to administration. An accurately measured dose of ~250 µg of ^{70}Zn was administered by mouth (PO) in the morning at least 2 h after eating. One hour after the oral isotope was given, an accurately measured dose of ~300 µg ^{67}Zn was administered intravenously (IV) via the antecubital or a pedal vein. Any losses of the oral or IV isotope in blood and saliva were collected on ashless filter paper and analyzed in order to determine the exact dose size (see below for sample analyses). All isotopes were prepared and administered using zinc-free materials. No food or breastmilk was consumed for the two-hour period before giving the oral isotope and during the one-hour period between administration of the oral and IV tracers.

Sample Collection: One 5-mL blood sample was collected 2-5 h following the IV infusion. Complete urine and fecal collections were initiated when the oral isotope was consumed and continued for the 24 hours in the CTU. The infants wore zinc-free urine bags during the 24-h collections. The sampling procedures were similar to other published stable isotope studies in this population and setting (15, 16). Health workers were trained by the researchers from University of Colorado on using zinc-free materials, and methods to attach and detach urine and stool bags to avoid contamination. The date, time, and unique notes about each sample were recorded on the participant's data collection form. If two fecal samples were not passed by the infant during the 24-h period, the infants stayed in the CTU until two samples were obtained. Following the urine and stool collections, the infants were discharged to their homes. Trained research staff visited the infants in their homes daily up to 9 d to collect two 30 mL urine samples, one in the morning and a second in the afternoon. They would wash the infant with soap and water, both zinc-free. Urine bags were attached using zinc-free

procedures and then the urine sample was collected and transferred directly into a zinc-free 60 ml Nalgene bottle. The Nalgene bottles were bagged in a zinc free Ziploc bag and taken directly to the field office where they were stored at -20 C until transferred (weekly) to the icddr,b main campus and stored at -20 C until shipment (on ice) to the University of Colorado for analyses.

Sample Analyses: All samples and doses were analysed at the University of Colorado. Total zinc concentration in serum and zinc stable isotope ratios ($^{67}\text{Zn}/^{66}\text{Zn}$ and $^{70}\text{Zn}/^{66}\text{Zn}$) were measured by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS, Agilent 7700x, Santa Clara, CA). Urine samples were purified prior to ICP-MS analysis, by digestion in a MARS microwave digestion system (CEM Corp, Matthews, NC) and zinc was separated from other elements by a chelation method (13). Total zinc in urine was measured by flame atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AAAnalyst 400; Perkin-Elmer Corp, Norwalk, CT). Stool samples were ashed, reconstituted in 6M HCl and analysed for zinc concentration by flame atomic absorption spectrophotometry. The reconstituted samples were then purified using column chromatography and the isotope ratios were analysed with ICP-MS (17). Ratios were converted to enrichments using a mathematical matrix which takes into account the natural and enriched zinc content of the dose (18).

Data Analysis and Modeling: The percent of oral and intravenous isotopic zinc dose in each sample was calculated from isotope enrichment and zinc concentrations. The isotope enrichment of the spot urine samples, a proxy of serum enrichment (19), was used to calculate the percent of the isotopic dose in serum to 9 d.

The kinetic data were analyzed using WinSAAM (20) and compartmental analysis (see Supplemental Digital Content 1 for a description of the model and model fitting). Data from serum, urine and feces for each infant were fitted by the model using the set of parameter values for non-stunted infants (10), and the parsimony principle of only allowing the minimum number of changes that were both necessary and sufficient to explain the new data. The model was fit by least squares analysis (Supplemental Digital Content 2 shows the model fit to observed data from a representative infant) and zinc kinetics were estimated. Fractional Zn absorption was determined for tracer (administered in solution, 2 h after a meal), and for tracee (i.e., zinc in meals), using the ratio of zinc movement into blood vs. down the gastrointestinal tract (Supplementary Digital Content 1 provides the equations in terms of fractional transfer coefficients).

$$\text{Daily Intake in food (mg Zn/d)} = \text{zinc excreted in urine} + \text{feces} + \text{growth} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Absorbed Zn (mg/d)} = \text{fractional absorption of tracee} \times \text{calculated daily Zn intake} \quad (2a)$$

As absorbed zinc was the amount required to maintain steady state (i.e., constant pool sizes) it also equalled the sum of zinc losses,

$$\text{Absorbed Zn (mg/d)} = \text{Zn excreted in urine} + \text{endogenous fecal excretion} + \text{growth} \quad (2b)$$

Urinary excretion (mg Zn/d), fecal excretion (mg Zn/d), endogenous fecal excretion (mg Zn/d) and pool masses (mg) were calculated using the model (see Supplementary Digital Content 1 for the equations).

The relationship between absorbed zinc and calculated zinc intake for infants was calculated in WinSAAM using the following equation;

$$\text{Absorbed Zn (mg/d)} = (A_{\max} \times \text{ZI}) / (IA_{50} + \text{ZI}) \quad (3)$$

Where A_{\max} is the maximum absorption of zinc, ZI is zinc intake (mg/d) and IA_{50} is the quantity of zinc (mg/d) required for half-maximal absorption (21).

Results are expressed as mean \pm SD. Infant characteristics and zinc kinetics were evaluated against LAZ using robust regression analysis (M Estimation) and SAS (version 9.4, SAS Corp Carey, N.C). A P value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Simulations: The published dynamic version of the model of infant zinc metabolism (i.e., with homeostatic functions) (10) was updated with parameter values that were correlated with LAZ scores and then used to predict the growth of stunted infants with zinc supplementation.

RESULTS

Ten infants 8-11 months of age were studied between February and October 2019. Their LAZ score ranged from -2.90 to -0.43 (**Table 1**). Two infants were LAZ > -2 , eight were LAZ ≤ -2 . None of the infants were wasted (WLZ ≤ -2 , Table 1). Serum zinc concentration and urinary zinc excretion were correlated with LAZ scores (Table 1 **and Figure 1**). The size of all the pools of zinc were also correlated with LAZ (Supplemental Digital Content 3 lists the amount of zinc in serum, muscle, bone and liver pools).

The fractional absorption of zinc tracer, given as a small amount of zinc in the postabsorptive state did not correlate with LAZ, nor did the calculated daily zinc intake (Table 1). However both the tracee fraction and the amount of zinc absorbed from the calculated daily intake correlated with LAZ (Table 1 and Figure 1). When the amount of zinc absorbed was plotted against calculated zinc intake, the amount absorbed by

stunted infants did not increase with calculated intake (**Figure 2**). For the eight infants with $LAZ \leq -2$ A_{max} was 0.29 mg/d and IA_{50} was 0.20 mg/d.

Changes were predicted in fractional zinc absorption, zinc absorbed, plasma zinc concentration and LAZ for stunted infants with, and without, zinc supplement by the dynamic model for zinc metabolism (**Figure 3**). With no supplement, the fraction and amount of zinc absorbed was unchanged but, because of infant growth, plasma zinc declined, to $< 65 \mu\text{g/L}$ after about 90 d and LAZ declined to -3 after 60 d. With a supplement of 5 mg Zn/d fractional absorption of daily zinc intake decreased to 0.04, absorbed zinc remained at 0.28 mg/d, plasma zinc declined, and LAZ remained < -2.5 . With 10 mg/d supplement fractional absorption decreased further, to 0.02 and, because the amount of zinc absorbed was similar to that from 5 mg/d supplement, the changes in plasma zinc and LAZ were similar to those of 5 mg/d supplement. When the absorption profile, (i.e., A_{max} and IA_{50} , Equation 3) of the infants with $LAZ \leq -2$, or stunted, was replaced by the values for non-stunted infants for healthy absorption and no supplement was given, the amount of zinc absorbed increased to 0.8 mg/d and plasma zinc increased to over $90 \mu\text{g/dL}$ however LAZ remained < -2.5 . However, when a supplement of 5 mg Zn/d was given with healthy absorption, even though fractional absorption decreased, absorbed zinc, plasma zinc and LAZ all increased and reached $LAZ > -2$ after 65 d. Thus, the LAZ of zinc-deficient, stunted infants was restored to non-stunted value of $LAZ > -2$ with healthy absorption and providing a supplement. We note that small amounts of zinc in aqueous form (i.e., tracer) given postabsorptively was absorbed as in non-stunted infants, while larger amounts of zinc in food (i.e., prandially) was limited in the stunted infants. We are unable to discern whether larger amounts of

zinc in aqueous form and/or given postabsorptively may be absorbed better. The simulations assumed that the supplement was given with food.

DISCUSSION

The main findings of this study are that serum zinc concentration, urinary zinc excretion, zinc pool sizes and the amount of zinc absorbed are correlated with LAZ in 8-11 mo old Bangladeshi infants. Dietary zinc intake was not correlated with LAZ. The stunted infants, unlike published results for non-stunted infants (21) did not absorb more zinc from higher zinc intake. The amount of zinc absorbed by the stunted infants had a V_{max} that was only 15% of that of non-stunted infants. This suggests that stunted infants have impaired zinc absorption.

The reason for the low zinc absorption by the stunted infants was most likely related to gut health (22), and specifically EED. EED likely affects nutrient absorption as it is characterized by mucosal inflammation, reduced surface area, and increased intestinal permeability (4). It is a concern in the area of our study as fractional zinc absorption by Bangladeshi 18-24 mo-old toddlers (from an aqueous dose of 3 mg zinc administered in the fasted state) was associated with biomarkers of gut health, i.e., inflammation and gut permeability (16). Another study showed that most Bangladeshi toddlers with lower zinc absorption had intestinal inflammation (15).

Our study showed that fractional absorption from tracer amounts of zinc was not related to LAZ. That is, all infants absorbed small amounts of zinc equally well when it was given in an aqueous solution in the fasted state, but as described above, stunted infants absorbed less zinc than non-stunted infants when the amounts of zinc were

larger and provided as food. Thus, the lower absorption by stunted than non-stunted infants could be influenced by the amount of zinc and/or timing of zinc intake (prandial or post absorptive) in addition to the form (soluble or as food). In non-stunted infants in Burkina Faso soluble zinc supplements increased plasma zinc concentration more in infants with better gut health (23). Those authors concluded that although intestinal permeability may reduce dietary zinc absorption it does not undermine the efficacy of (soluble) zinc supplements. Likewise, the parent trial also reported that plasma zinc increased more with dispersible zinc tablets than with micronutrient powders mixed with food (24).

We simulated the effects of zinc supplementation using our dynamic model (10). The model was developed using published data to derive increases in tissue pools of zinc with growth and homeostatic adjustments in zinc absorption and excretion with zinc intake. Using the A_{max} and AI_{50} values determined from this study, we predicted that linear growth of stunted infants would only increase with zinc supplementation when zinc absorption kinetics were set to the A_{max} and AI_{50} values for non-stunted infants, i.e., when the gut of stunted infants was healthy. We note that if the supplements were in a soluble form, more zinc may be absorbed, as the increase in plasma zinc with supplementation was related to gut health (23).

The correlation of serum zinc with LAZ would be expected as low plasma (or serum) zinc concentration and the prevalence of stunting are both considered indicators of zinc deficiency at the population-level (25); the proportions of children with stunting and with low plasma zinc concentrations were comparable in a micronutrient survey in Bangladesh (26). In a recent study Jongstra et al., (27) supplemented Bangladeshi

infants (60% stunted) aged 12-36 mo with 1 mg additional Zn/d using biofortified rice for 9 mo. They reported that plasma zinc concentrations declined over time with or without the supplement. We simulated a stunted 9-mo old infant supplemented with 0 or 1 mg additional Zn/d using our dynamic model, and also predicted that plasma zinc would decline to the same degree for both groups (data not shown). The model predicted that if absorption parameters were changed from the values for stunted infants, as found in the current study, to those of non-stunted infants plasma zinc would increase with 1 mg Zn/d supplement. The agreement of the model with those experimental results supports the findings of this study, that zinc absorption from food is impaired in stunted infants.

To our knowledge, this is the first report of zinc kinetics in 8-11 mo-old stunted infants. A strength of our study is that zinc kinetics were measured in infants of similar age, who were from the same population and who were not wasted, indicating that their caloric intakes were adequate. Limitations of the study were the number of infants. The number of stunted infants is consistent with other kinetic studies, as these studies require intensive sampling of each participant. Only two non-stunted infants were studied and although most analyses were across LAZ, for one (the relationship of absorbed zinc with zinc intake) values for stunted Bangladeshi infants were compared to non-stunted infants studied elsewhere. Dietary zinc was not measured but was deduced from the kinetic and zinc excretion data. The mean value is similar to that reported for preschool age infants of the area (2.6 ± 1.5 mg Zn/d) (9). Although fecal collections were only over 24 h, multiple (between 2-5) samples were obtained per infant suggesting a regular excretion pattern. EED status was not measured but as in toddlers, is likely to be present and to contribute to the reduced absorption (15). Some have argued that EED

contributes a relatively small amount to the total growth deficits (28) and that a combination of approaches are required to reduce stunting (29).

In conclusion, zinc kinetics in Bangladeshi infants correlate with LAZ and show that malabsorption of supplemental sources of zinc may occur in stunted infants.

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TABLE 1. Relationship to LAZ of infant characteristics and zinc kinetics (absorption, zinc in diet, absorbed and endogenously excreted zinc) calculated by the compartment model¹

Parameter	Range	Mean	SD	r ²	Y intercept	Beta	P value
LAZ	-2.9 to -0.43	-2.11	0.72				
Age, mo	8 to 11	9.00	0.94	0.063	8.26	-0.32	0.46
Weight, kg	6.67 to 8.31	7.39	0.64	0.522	8.75	0.68	0.001
Length, cm	63.8 to 72.2	67.1	2.42	0.595	73.15	2.93	0.001
WLZ	-0.99 to 0.41	-0.45	0.50	0.032	-0.76	-0.13	0.6
WAZ	-2.12 to -0.51	-1.54	0.51	0.418	-0.58	0.46	0.01
Serum Zn, µg/dL	54.3 to 117.6	81.0	18.77	0.599	131.2	24.4	0.001
Urine Zn, mg/d	0.036 to 0.219	0.114	0.059	0.430	0.25	0.06	0.01
Fecal Zn, mg/d	0.79 to 4.75	2.36	1.34	0.147	0.738	-0.68	0.23
Tracer Absorption, fraction	0.45 to 0.86	0.70	0.13	0.137	0.850	0.07	0.24
Tracee Absorption, fraction	0.06 to 0.41	0.16	0.11	0.333	0.320	0.08	0.030
Zn Intake, mg/d	1.21 to 4.96	2.62	1.29	0.110	1.250	-0.57	0.33
Absorbed Zn, mg/d	0.19 to 0.50	0.33	0.10	0.465	0.543	0.11	0.0080

Endogenous Zn Excretion, mg/d	0.02 to 0.09	0.07	0.02	0.028	0.055	-0.005	0.62
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¹N=10. Compartmental model in Supplemental Digital Content 1. Data were analyzed by robust regression. Zinc intake was calculated as the sum of zinc excreted in urine, excreted in feces and used for growth (see Equation 1).

LAZ, length-for-age z score; WAZ, weight-for-age z score; WLZ, weight-for-length z score; Zn, zinc.

FIGURE LEGENDS

FIGURE 1 Values plotted against length-for-age z scores (LAZ) for serum zinc concentration (A), urine zinc (B), fractional absorption of tracee zinc (C) and zinc in pool 1 (D). The lines were determined by robust regression.

FIGURE 2 The relationship between absorbed zinc and calculated zinc intake for infants. Symbols are data of infants from this study $LAZ \leq -2$ ($n=8$). The lines were calculated using Equation 3. The line for non-stunted infants is based on many studies in the literature (10, 21). (For the two non-stunted infants zinc intake was 1.21 mg/d and 1.94 mg/d and absorbed zinc was 0.50 and 0.49 mg/d). A_{max} was 0.29 mg/d (compared to 1.9 mg/d for non-stunted infants (21)) and IA_{50} was 0.20 mg/d (compared to 3.5 mg/d for non-stunted infants (10, 21))

FIGURE 3 Predictions by the dynamic model (10) for changes in absorption fraction (A), absorbed zinc (B), plasma zinc (C) and LAZ (D) of stunted infants with zinc supplementation. The model predicted that with no supplement, LAZ of stunted infants would continue to decline over time, and that zinc supplementation would only improve LAZ when the A_{max} and IA_{50} of absorption (see Equation 3) were restored to the values of non-stunted infants (D).

Supplementary Digital Content Legend

Supplementary Digital Content 1, Figure

Supplemental Digital Content 2, Figure

Supplemental Digital Content 3, Table

A

B

C

D

Figure 1

—▲— LAZ ≤ -2 - - - - LAZ > -2

Figure 2

Figure 3

SDC FIGURE 1. Compartmental model for zinc metabolism in infants (adapted from (1)); circles represent pools (the numbers in the circles are arbitrary), the arrows represent movement of zinc between pools. Compartments 23, 24 and 25 are in the gastrointestinal tract. Compartment 29 is a delay before tracer is excreted in urine. Labels by the pools were determined from adult studies with zinc radiotracer that allowed external counting over the liver and thigh (muscle and bone) areas (2). Labels in parentheses were identified through animal studies (3). The double arrow into compartment 23 represents site of entry of zinc in food (this value was calculated by the model). The arrows with an asterisk indicate the site of tracer entry, oral tracer into compartment 23 and IV tracer into compartment 1. As described (1), in the steady state version of the model, there is a small loss out of compartment 1 of 0.6/d (not shown) representing growth. Values of pathways were as listed in the model description (1)

except for values of the bold arrows, which differed in this study between infants. The infants were assumed to be in steady state over the 10-d study period, the parameters remained constant over time and homeostatic functions were not included in the model. Growth is represented by a single loss pathway (for longer-term studies it is represented by non-linear functions on tissue uptake of zinc (1)). The model included pools of zinc connected by pathways, called transfer coefficients, $L(i,j)$ that represent the fraction moving into pool i from pool j per unit time. The tracer data for each infant were fitted by two forms of the model that differed only in the site of tracer entry (by mouth or intravenously), and the value of the pathway for movement from the intestine into plasma, $L(1,24)$. This allowed for absorption of zinc tracer, (zinc given in aqueous solution in the fasted state), to differ from absorption of zinc tracee (zinc in meals).

Data from serum, urine and feces were fitted by the model for each infant. Published parameter values for infants (1) were used except for the following parameters that were allowed to differ for each infant: volume of distribution (i.e., the volume that the tracer initially distributes in), absorption of tracer and tracee, urine excretion, endogenous fecal excretion and fecal excretion (the pathways are highlighted). The model was fit by least squares analysis and then used to calculate pool masses, $M(i)$, and,

$$\text{Fractional Zn absorption} = (L(1,24))/(L(1,24) + L(25,24)) \quad (1)$$

Fractional Zn absorption was determined for tracer (administered in solution, 2 h after a meal), and for tracee (i.e., zinc in meals).

$$\text{Urinary excretion (mg Zn/d)} = L(29,1) \times M(1) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Fecal excretion (mg Zn/d)} = L(4,25) \times M(25) \quad (3)$$

Endogenous fecal excretion (mg Zn/d)

$$= (L(24,1) \times M(1)) \times (1 - \text{fraction tracee absorbed}) \quad (4)$$

Parameter values (mean \pm SD) that were different for this population than values reported previously and not correlated with LAZ were; volume of distribution 0.80 ± 0.21 L, or 0.11 ± 0.03 L/kg, $L(1,24)$ (for tracer) 12 ± 7 /d, $L(24,1)$ 0.34 ± 0.11 /d, $L(29,1)$ 0.46 ± 0.15 /d, $L(12,29)$ 0.42 ± 0.15 /d and $L(4,25)$ 5.5 ± 4.1 /d.

References:

- 1 Wastney ME, McDonald CM, King JC A dynamic model for predicting growth in zinc-deficient stunted infants given supplemental zinc. *Am J Clin Nutr* 2018;107(5):808-16.
- 2 Wastney ME, Aamodt RL, Rumble WF, et al. Kinetic analysis of zinc metabolism and its regulation in normal humans. *Am J Physiol* 1986;251(Reg. Integ. Comp. Physiol 20):R398-R408.
- 3 House WA, Wastney ME Compartmental analysis of zinc kinetics in mature male rats. *Am. J. Physiol* 1997;273(Reg. Integ. Comp. Physiol 42):R1117-R25.

Supplemental Digital Content 2

SDC 2, FIGURE. Fit of the model (Supplemental Digital Content 1, Figure) (lines) to a set of data (symbols) for one infant following oral and IV tracer in serum (A), urine (B), and feces (C), and excretion of zinc in feces and urine (D).

Supplemental Digital Content 3, Table

Zinc pool sizes calculated by the compartment model and relationship to LAZ¹

Infant	LAZ	Pool Zn ² , mg					
		1 (Serum)	3 (Muscle)	5 (RBC)	7 (Bone)	8 (Liver-1)	9 (Liver-2)
1	-2.90	0.23	139	0.34	15.8	1.2	3.2
2	-2.65	0.14	86	0.21	9.8	0.7	2.0
3	-2.52	0.21	124	0.30	14.1	1.1	2.8
4	-2.39	0.20	117	0.28	13.3	1.0	2.7
5	-2.37	0.20	120	0.29	13.7	1.0	2.7
6	-2.28	0.23	134	0.32	15.3	1.1	3.1
7	-2.20	0.24	140	0.34	15.9	1.2	3.2
8	-1.99	0.23	137	0.33	15.6	1.2	3.1
9	-1.39	0.35	206	0.50	23.4	1.8	4.7
10	-0.43	0.39	231	0.56	26.3	2.0	5.2
Mean	-2.11	0.24	144	0.35	16.3	1.22	3.26
SD	0.72	0.07	43	0.10	4.9	0.37	0.98
r ²		0.629	0.629	0.629	0.632	0.619	0.619
Y intercept		0.44	258.5	0.63	29.4	2.25	5.82
Beta		0.09	55.86	0.14	6.36	0.49	1.24
P-value		0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001

¹Compartmental model (described in Figure Supplemental Digital Content 1). Data were analyzed by robust regression. LAZ, length-for-age z score

²The r² values of the pools with LAZ were the same as plasma because tissue exchanges with plasma did not differ between infants, and so pool sizes were relative to plasma.